

Milestone 34: Completion of evaluation of Calls 3, 4 & 5

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1 Introduction

ATMO-ACCESS (Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities) provides opportunities to access some of the most advanced atmospheric research facilities in Europe. These include ground-based observatories, mobile platforms, atmospheric simulation chambers, and central laboratories for analyses and calibrations. ATMO-ACCESS offers free of charge access to these facilities, including specific training in addition to the logistical, technological, and scientific support. Users may also benefit from a contribution to their travel and local subsistence costs.

During the project, ATMO-ACCESS opened more calls for Trans-National Access (TNA) than originally planned. Therefore, this document (MS34, initially entitled *Completion of evaluation of third call*) reports about the evaluation of the applications to Calls 3, 4 and 5, which were all completed by the date this report was due (31st March 2024).

2 Description of the application evaluation process for Calls 3, 4 and 5

Proposals for TNA were evaluated on the basis of specific application forms filled in by the applicants using the PASS platform. All applications went through an evaluation process consisting of 4 steps:

- 1) Eligibility check by the Service and Access Management Unit (SAMU) [1], where the overall eligibility of the application was verified, according to TNA rules in H2020.
- 2) Feasibility check by the access provider to the requested facility, in terms of technical capacity, agenda, human resources, etc.
- 3) External review performed by experts selected from the Access Evaluation Panel (AEP) [2], whose composition and functioning are further described in ATMO-ACCESS Deliverable 9.1 [3]. Experts were asked to award points to each proposal according to the following groups of criteria per relevant access evaluation mode:
 - scientific relevance
 - technical value
 - novelty and innovation
 - applicants' quality
 - learning objectives.

ATMO-ACCESS application forms guide applicants to provide the reviewers with the information needed to evaluate their proposals based on the criteria listed above.

Ideally 3 reviews were solicited for each application, but this was found to be challenging and in practice, only around ¼ of all proposals received 3 full reviews.

A rapporteur was appointed among the reviewers, with the task of balancing and summarizing the reviewers' assessment reports.

- 4) The final selection was made by the ATMO-ACCESS Strategic Trans-national and Virtual Access Board (STVB), with the support of the project Coordination and the SAMU (in charge of TNA management).

ATMO-ACCESS evaluation criteria (or their weight) depended on the driver of the access request, namely scientific excellence, technical need, innovation and market, and training need.

2.1 Evaluation of call #3

Call #3 was open from October 10th, 2022 to January 5th, 2023. The call was a generic one, without any specific topic. Physical (and/or remote) access to 52 European atmospheric research facilities was offered with no further constraint, although new and unconventional access to facilities were encouraged, as usual, by allocating up to 5 points during the evaluation process. Sixty-four (64) applications were submitted in due time, involving 193 users and 30 facilities, relating to access to observatories (55%), simulation chambers (31%), central laboratories (9%), and mobile platforms (5%).

The proposal evaluation process started as soon as the call was closed, and was completed according to the agenda planned by the project coordination (Fig. 2.1.1). Proposals were first individually evaluated by 61 experts from the ATMO-ACCESS AEP. The five applications (8%) for which less than 2 reviews from the AEP were received were additionally reviewed by 1 to 4 members of the ATMO-ACCESS STVB. The final selection was made based on these reviews during a dedicated meeting of the STVB held on February 28th, 2023. The meeting focused on the appraisal of those applications getting a number of points close to the accept/reject threshold. Forty-two (42) proposals were eventually selected (66% success rate). Applicants were notified the results of the selection process by SAMU on March 7th, 2023, through the PASS platform.

Figure 2.1.1: Timeline of the evaluation process of the 3rd call for TNA.

Table 2.1.1 shows the success rate of applications under call #3 according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed. Access to observational platforms in the Scientific Excellence category were by far the most requested (45% of all applications). It can be noted that the applications to access mobile platforms were all accepted (3/3), and that applications driven by technical needs were almost all accepted (5/6). In contrast, half of the applications driven by training needs were rejected (3/6).

Table 2.1.1: Success rate of applications under the 3rd call according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed.

	Research and Innovation	Technical Services	Training Services	All Categories
Observatories	62%	100%	40%	61%
Atmospheric Simulation Chambers	72%	100%	100%	75%
Mobile Platforms	100%	100%	N/A	100%
Central Laboratories	50%	50%	N/A	50%
All Facilities	66%	83%	50%	66%

2.2 Evaluation of call #4

Call #4 was open from February 27th to May 15th, 2023. It was focused on remote and hybrid (i.e., partly remote and partly physical) access to the ATMO-ACCESS facilities. This call was particularly aimed at testing the attractiveness of the remote mode of access, which can be sometimes particularly efficient and cost-effective. Thirty-one (31) applications were submitted in due time (i.e., less than half compared to the open Call #3), involving 100 users. Applications concerned access to observatories (48%), simulation chambers (32%) and central laboratories (19%). There were no applications for remote/hybrid access to mobile platforms.

The evaluation process proceeded as initially planned by the ATMO-ACCESS project coordination. Proposals were rated by 34 experts from the AEP, supplemented by members of the STVB for the 3 applications evaluated by less than two reviewers from the AEP. Applications were eventually selected based on these evaluations during a dedicated meeting of the STVB, the project Coordinator, and SAMU held on June 19th, 2023 (Fig. 2.2.1). Nine (9) applications did not fulfil the rules set by ATMO-ACCESS, and one (1) proposal was not feasible. Twenty-one (21) proposals were eventually selected (68% success rate). Actually, only 6 applications (19%) were rejected based on technical and/or scientific criteria. Applicants were notified the results of the selection process by SAMU on June 22nd, 2023, via the PASS platform.

Figure 2.2.1: Timeline of the evaluation process of the 4th call for TNA.

Table 2.2.1 attempts to show the success rate of applications under call #4 according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed. Due to the rather small number of applications, the statistical significance of the figures in Table 2.2.1 is limited. It is worth noting that none of the applications for training were accepted because applicants were all from ACTRIS National Facilities requesting access to ACTRIS Central Facilities: this type of service is meant to be provided under of ACTRIS ERIC. The unique request for instrument development (market-driven) was deemed ineligible by the STVB and the Coordination and was accepted under the private sector call in July 2023.

Table 2.2.1: Success rate of applications under the 4th call according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed

	Research and Innovation	Technical Services	Training Services	All Categories
Observatories	89%	0%	0%	53%
Atmospheric Simulation Chambers	100%	N/A	N/A	100%
Mobile Platforms	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Central Laboratories	100%	50%	0%	50%
All Facilities	95%	20%	0%	68%

2.3 Evaluation of call #5

Call #5 was open from July 12th to September 25th, 2023. Access to 56 European atmospheric research facilities (including 9 new platforms) was offered with no constraint, while new and unconventional access to facilities was encouraged as always. Fifty-one (51) applications were submitted in due time, involving 174 users and 29 facilities. They related to access to observational platforms (59%), simulation chambers (33%), central laboratories (6%), and mobile platforms (2%).

The proposal evaluation process started immediately after the call was closed. Two applications did not enter the external evaluation phase. One application was deemed ineligible because it came from a national ACTRIS facility requesting a service from a unit of the reference Central Facility. The other application was deemed not feasible by the provider. Therefore, forty-nine (49) applications were evaluated by 55 reviewers from the AEP. Eight proposals (17%) got reviewed by less than two reviewers from the AEP, and were each rated by 1 or 2 members of the STVB within 9 days after the date planned by the project coordination (Fig. 2.3.1). The final

selection was made based on reviews by the AEP (and the STVB when necessary) during a dedicated meeting of the STVB on November 9th, 2023. The main purpose of the meeting was to set the numerical threshold for accepting/rejecting proposals high enough in order to select only proposals getting a clearly positive appraisal from the reviewers. Thirty-nine (39) proposals were eventually selected (76% success rate). Applicants were notified the results of the selection process by SAMU on November 23rd, 2023, through the PASS platform.

Figure 2.3.1: Timeline of the evaluation process of the 5th call for TNA.

Table 2.3.1 shows the success rate of applications under call #5 according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed. Access to observational platforms in the Scientific Excellence category was by far the most requested (59% of all applications), which strongly influenced the overall statistics. There were unique requests to access mobile platforms and central laboratories for research purposes and both were accepted. In contrast, only 3 out of 4 requested for training passed. Requests to access observational platforms and simulation chambers were similarly successful (74% vs 78%).

Table 2.3.1: Success rate of applications under the 5th call according to their main driver and the type of facility to be accessed.

	Research and Innovation	Technical Services	Training Services	All
Observatories	72%	88%	75%	74%
Atmospheric Simulation Chambers	78%	N/A	N/A	78%
Mobile Platforms	100%	N/A	N/A	100%
Central Laboratories	100%	100%	N/A	50%
All	76%	88%	75%	76%

3 Conclusion

The evaluation of applications for access under calls 3, 4 and 5 was completed by the time MS34 was due (31st March 2024). Thanks to the experience gained from the first two calls, the selection process has been more consistent for calls 3, 4 and 5, which were eventually more competitive.

In total, 144 proposals were reviewed by 82 different reviewers in 10 months. All applications that were not reviewed by any independent expert from the AEP had previously been discarded upstream of the review process for ineligibility or unfeasibility. Only 24% of all applications (26%

of the eligible applications) were reviewed by 3 reviewers from the AEP as originally planned (Deliverable 9.1 [3]), but 85% (91% of the eligible applications) were reviewed by at least 2 reviewers from the AEP (Figure 3.1). There was a 10% decrease in the number of applications reviewed by at least 2 reviewers from the AEP for calls 4 and 5 as compared to call 3.

Figure 3.1: Percentages of applications getting 3, 2, 1 or no reviews from the AEP.

Members of the ATMO-ACCESS STVB and the Coordination supplemented the AEP when needed, so that each application was reviewed by at least 2 reviewers.

During the final selection meetings, the STVB noticed limitations of the review process by the AEP, among which:

- The appraisals by 2 different reviewers can be very diverging
- There is a certain degree of uncertainty in the numerical marks given by different reviewers
- Fairness is not guaranteed by the reviewing of the various applications by different reviewers.

Nonetheless, the STVB agreed not to modify the ranking coming from the review process of the AEP. Their decision was limited to setting a numerical value for the pass / no-pass threshold, so that only applications getting clearly positive appraisals were granted.

On average over calls 3, 4, and 5, there were large differences in the application success rate according to the type of facility requested, or the main driver for access. Access requests to mobile platforms were all granted (4/4) while half of the applications to use Central Laboratories (8/16) were rejected. The success rates of proposals to access observational platforms and

simulation chambers were not too different (57% and 67%, respectively). Likewise, were similarly successful the requests driven by scientific excellence and technical service needs (66% and 71%, respectively). In contrast, only 24% of applications for training TNA were eventually granted. This could be due to the lower experience of the applicants in writing proposals. A more in-depth analysis of the training TNA will be provided in the project final recommendations. However, adjustments of the evaluation grids could be needed to push up the success rate of requests for training.

4 References

- [1] Description of application, review and selection process for TNA to ATMO-ACCESS facilities, [ATMO-ACCESS Milestone 9.1](#)
- [2] [Terms of Reference for the ATMO-ACCESS Access Evaluation Panel](#), ATMO-ACCESS document.
- [3] Deliverable 9.1 in ATMO-ACCESS: [First assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities](#)
- [4] Deliverable 9.2 in ATMO-ACCESS: [Second assessment of TNA provided to ATMO-ACCESS facilities](#)
- [5] Deliverable 5.6 [ACTRIS Access and Service Management Plan](#)
- [6] [Updated ACTRIS User Strategy](#).

5 Annex I:

ATMO-ACCESS Evaluation Criteria and Scoring for calls 3, 4 and 5.

A. 3rd TNA Call evaluation criteria and scoring

A.1 Excellence-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum
1 - Scientific and technical value		15
a) Scientific and technical quality	Appropriateness, rationale, and completeness of the proposed scientific work. Degree to which it is based on sound scientific and technical principles. Quality of the work plan and approach for organization / implementation.	0-5
b) Impact on science	Degree to which results and the new knowledge is useful and may have a significant impact on the academic community, exploring creative, original, or potentially transformative concepts. Potential of the research project to go beyond the state of the art and open new scientific, technological or scholarly horizons.	0-5
c) Dissemination and exploitation plan	Are all possible targets of dissemination activities clearly identified (stakeholders that could uptake and make use of results)? Are the dissemination strategy and activities carefully planned, including the choice of suitable channels? Is there a plan for exploiting results in further research activities, or in developing new products/services?	0-5
2 - Novelty and innovation		15
a) Transdisciplinarity	Degree to which the proposed work identifies and builds/enables trans-disciplinary developments beyond atmospheric science. Are there any research projects in Europe or internationally related with the proposal? Are possible synergies and interactions described?	0-5
b) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical	0-5

	access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes).	
c) Potential for seeding links with industry and innovation	Degree to which the proposed work shows potential for industrial applications, for contributing to new technology development, for prototype testing.	0-5
3 - Quality of the applicant		20
a) Scientific qualification / track-record of the user group	Research track-record, professional background, references, capabilities and experience of the user group leader and members. Degree to which the group presents a balanced participation of experienced and non-experienced users, who have the chance to learn from the others.	0-5
b) Gender balance	Degree to which the proposal is built on a balanced participation, as close as possible to 50/50, of both men and women in the team and among the leading roles.	0-5
c) Collaboration and access to new Users	Degree to which the group includes: i) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; ii) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. iii) users from non-atmospheric/non-academic domains	0-5
d) Involvement of students / young scientists	Are early career scientists and students at PhD level and below involved in the project? Are they taking roles of responsibility? Is there any specific training for them?	0-5

A.2 Technical need-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum
1 - Technical and scientific relevance		25
a) Relevance of the instrument	Measurement needs served by the instrument and/or geographical pertinence.	0-5
b) Frequency of the technical need	Is the requested service scheduled, required or recommended to continue ensure quality measurements?	0-5

c) Training for the staff using the instrument	Is training for the staff planned? Are proposals for such training innovative (i.e., remote training while the service occurs, etc.)?	0-5
d) Interest to the scientific community	Degree to which the requested service is useful to meet the quality expectations of a particular science community and/or end-users for the exploitation of data.	0-5
e) Dissemination plan: availability and use of data	Are the plans for a high-level exploitation of the instrument adequate? Is there any plan to make data and measurements supported by the instrument openly available through deposition in trusted repositories?	0-5
2 - Quality of the applicant		15
a) References and experience of the user group	Research/measurements track-record and professional background	0-5
b) Gender balance	Degree to which the proposal is built on a balanced participation, as close as possible to 50/50, of both men and women in the team and among the leading roles.	0-5
c) Collaboration and access to new Users	Degree to which the user group includes: i) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; ii) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. iii) users from non-academic domain.	0-5

A.3 Market-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores/ maximum
1 - Scientific and Technical value		10
a) Scientific and technical quality	Is the proposed work based on a sound knowledge of the state of the art? Is the realization of the proposed solution/work realistic, considering the available knowledge, technical resources and expertise?	0-5
b) Dissemination and exploitation plan	Is there a clear future strategy for knowledge management and protection (IP strategy)? Does the proposed work include a credible path to deliver the (innovative) solution to the	0-5

	market? (i.e. adequacy of plans for commercialization and utilization of the proposed solution).	
2 - Innovation and Market potential		20
a) Likelihood of developing a new successful technology/product	The extent to which the proposed project will lead to new and improved products, processes or services with clear market potential.	0-5
b) Anticipated benefits of the proposed work in comparison to current commercial and emerging technologies	Is the solution a significant improvement over previous/other ongoing alternatives? Has it some potential to change the dynamic of the market and possibly to address a societal challenge?	0-5
c) Market potential	How large is the population that will be interested in the technology/product/service being developed? Has it been clearly identified? Is the solution suitable to satisfy the market need?	0-5
d) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes)	0-5
3 - Quality of the applicant		15
a) References, capabilities and experience of the user group/company	Track-record and professional background, company profile.	0-5
b) Gender balance	Degree to which the proposal is built on a balanced participation, as close as possible to 50/50, of both men and women in the teams and among the leading roles	0-5
c) Collaboration and access to new Users	Degree to which the group includes: i) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; ii) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. iii) users from non-atmospheric domains	0-5

A.4 Training need-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Marks / maximum
1 - Scientific/learning objectives and motivation		20
a) Relevance of the scientific and training objectives	Appropriateness, motivation, and completeness of the objectives of the proposed training.	0-5
b) Relevance of the training for the user current/future position	Degree to which the training is needed/useful and may have a significant impact on the applicants' career path. Would the applicants utilize knowledge and expertise gained regularly?	0-5
c) Relevance of the training for the belonging organization	Degree to which the training is needed/useful for the applicants' organization.	0-5
c) Multiplier effect of the training	Degree to which the applicant could be counted on to further disseminate the knowledge and expertise gained (train the trainer).	0-5
2 - Quality of the applicant		25
a) Academic achievement	Evidence from CV or references of higher degrees, publications, honors, awards and scholarships, research experience. Knowledge and expertise	0-5
b) Gender balance	Degree to which the proposal is built on a balanced participation, as close as possible to 50/50, of both men and women in the team and among the leading roles.	0-5
c) Collaboration and access to new Users	Degree to which the group includes: i) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; ii) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. iii) users from non-atmospheric/non-academic domains	0-5
d) Involvement of students / young scientists	Are early career scientists and students at PhD level and below involved in the project? Are they taking roles of responsibility? Is there any specific training for them?	0-5
e) Potential for seeding links with industry and innovation	Degree to which the proposed work shows potential for industrial applications, for contributing to new technology development, for prototype testing.	0-5

B. 4th TNA Call evaluation criteria and scoring

B. 1 Excellence-driven access

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum
1 - Scientific and technical value		20
a) Scientific and technical quality	Appropriateness, rationale, and completeness of the proposed scientific work. Degree to which it is based on sound scientific and technical principles. Quality of the work plan and approach for organization / implementation.	0-5
b) Impact on science	Degree to which results and the new knowledge is useful and may have a significant impact on the academic community, exploring creative, original, or potentially transformative concepts. Potential of the research project to go beyond the state of the art and open new scientific, technological or scholarly horizons.	0-5
c) Dissemination and exploitation plan	Are all possible targets of dissemination activities clearly identified (stakeholders that could uptake and make use of results)? Are the dissemination strategy and activities carefully planned, including the choice of suitable channels? Is there a plan for exploiting results in further research activities, or in developing new products/services?	0-5
d) Scientific qualification / track-record of the user group	Research track-record, professional background, references, capabilities and experience of the user group leader and members. Degree to which the group presents a balanced participation of experienced and non-experienced users, who have the chance to learn from the others.	0-5
2 - Novelty and innovation		15

a) X-disciplinarity	Degree to which the proposed work identifies and builds/enables X-disciplinary developments beyond atmospheric science. Are there any research projects in Europe or internationally related with the proposal? Are possible synergies and interactions described?	0-5
b) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes).	0-5
c) Potential for seeding links with industry and innovation	Degree to which the proposed work shows potential for industrial applications, for contributing to new technology development, for prototype testing.	0-5

B.2 Technical need-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum
1 - Technical need		15
a) Relevance/Frequency of the technical need	Is the requested service scheduled, required or recommended to continue ensure quality measurements?	0-5
b) Training for the staff using the instrument	Is training for the staff planned? Are proposals for such training innovative (i.e., remote training while the service occurs, etc.)?	0-5
c) References and experience of the user group	Research/measurements track-record and professional background	0-5
2 - Scientific relevance		15
a) Relevance of the instrument	Measurement needs served by the instrument and/or geographical pertinence.	0-5
b) Interest to the scientific community	Degree to which the requested service is useful to meet the quality expectations of a particular science community and/or end-users for the exploitation of data.	0-5

c) Dissemination plan: availability and use of data	Are the plans for a high-level exploitation of the instrument adequate? Is there any plan to make data and measurements supported by the instrument openly available through deposition in trusted repositories?	0-5
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B.3 Market-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum
1 - Scientific and Technical value		15
a) Scientific and technical quality	Is the proposed work based on a sound knowledge of the state of the art? Is the realization of the proposed solution/work realistic, considering the available knowledge, technical resources and expertise?	0-5
b) Quality of the workplan and exploitation plan	Appropriateness, rationale, and completeness of the proposed scientific work. Does the proposed work include a credible path to deliver the (innovative) solution to the market? (i.e. adequacy of plans for commercialization and utilization of the proposed solution). Is there a clear future strategy for knowledge management and protection (IP strategy)?	0-5
c) References, capabilities and experience of the user group/company	Track-record and professional background, company profile.	0-5
2 - Innovation and Market potential		15
a) Likelihood of developing a new successful technology/product	The extent to which the proposed project will lead to new and improved products, processes or services with clear market potential.	0-5
b) Market potential (Anticipated benefits of the proposed work in comparison to current commercial and emerging technologies)	Is the solution a significant improvement over previous/other ongoing alternatives? Has it some potential to change the dynamic of the market and possibly to address a societal challenge?	0-5

c) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes)	0-5
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B.4 Training need-driven access mode

Criterion	Explanation	Scores / maximum	
1 - Scientific/learning objectives and motivation 15			 ATMO_6th_call_result s.xlsx
a) Relevance of the scientific and training objectives	Appropriateness, motivation, and completeness of the objectives of the proposed training.	0-5	
b) Relevance of the training for the user current/future position	Degree to which the training is needed/useful and may have a significant impact on the applicants' career path. Would the applicants utilize knowledge and expertise gained regularly? How are the plans for exploiting the knowledge and skills acquired?	0-5	
c) Relevance of the training for the belonging organization (multiplier effect of the training)	Degree to which the training is needed/useful for the operations/developments of the organization the users belong to. Degree to which the applicant could be counted on to further disseminate the knowledge and expertise gained (train the trainer).	0-5	
2 - Quality of the applicant 10			
a) Academic achievement	Evidence from CV or references of higher degrees, publications, honors, awards and scholarships, research experience. Knowledge and expertise	0-5	
		0-5	

b) Research potential	Applicant's ability to conduct independent research and contribute to the field. This can be evaluated based on their research interests, previous research experience, and any publications or conference presentations.	
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B.5 BONUS POINTS added to any application.

BONUS points to be added (by SAMU) to the average scores obtained after review		MAX 3	Rule for scoring
i) For Gender empowerment	In case of: a) female/non-binary leadership of the user group b) user groups composed of the majority of women c) 50%-50% gender balance in the user group	1	If at least one of a), b), c) is YES then score 1 Otherwise no score
ii) For collaboration and access to new Users	In case of: a) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; b) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. c) users from non-atmospheric/non-academic domains	1	If at least one of a), b), c) is YES then score 1 Otherwise no score.
iii) For involvement of students / young scientists	In case of: a) early career scientists and students at PhD level and below involved in the project	1	If a) is YES then score 1 Otherwise no score.

C. 5th TNA Call evaluation criteria and scoring

C. 1 Excellence-driven access

Criterion	Explanation	Score / Points available
1 - Scientific and technical value		30
		0-10

a) Scientific and technical quality	Clarity and pertinence of the scientific objectives. Appropriateness and rationale of the proposed scientific work. Degree to which it is based on sound scientific and technical principles.	
b) Impact on science	Degree to which results and the new knowledge are useful and may have a significant impact on the academic community, exploring creative, original, or potentially transformative concepts. Potential of the research project to go beyond the state of the art and open new scientific, technological or scholarly horizons.	0-10
c) X-disciplinarity	Degree to which the proposed work identifies and builds/enables X-disciplinary developments beyond atmospheric science. Are there any research projects in Europe or internationally related to the proposal? Are possible synergies and interactions described?	0-10
2 - Novelty and innovation		15
a) Use of new technology, methodology, or innovative approaches in data interpretation	Degree to which the proposed work makes use of new technologies, methodologies or explores innovative measurement / data evaluation approaches.	0-5
b) Potential for seeding links with industry and innovation	Degree to which the proposed work shows potential for industrial applications, for contributing to new technology development, for prototype testing.	0-5
c) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes).	0-5
3 -Quality and efficiency of the implementation		6
a) Quality of the workplan and dissemination plan	Quality and effectiveness of the work plan. Feasibility of the approach and activities to be developed. Recipients of dissemination clearly identified	0-3

	(stakeholders that could uptake and make use of results) and activities carefully planned.	
b) Scientific qualification/ track-record of the user group	Research track-record, professional background, references, capabilities and experience of the user group leader and members. Degree to which the group presents a balanced participation of experienced and non-experienced users, who have the chance to learn from the others and be trained.	0-3

C. 2 Technical need-driven access

Criterion	Explanation	Score / Points available
1- Scientific relevance		30
a) Relevance of the instrument	Measurement needs served by the instrument and/or geographical pertinence.	0-10
b) Interest to the scientific community	Degree to which the requested service is useful to meet the quality expectations of a particular science community and/or end-users for the exploitation of data.	0-10
c) Availability and use of data (Dissemination plan)	Are the plans for a high-level exploitation of the instrument adequate? Is there any plan to make data and measurements supported by the instrument openly available through deposition in trusted repositories?	0-10
2 - Technical need		15
a) Frequency of the technical need	Is the requested service scheduled, required or recommended to continue ensure quality measurements?	0-5

b) Training for the staff using the instrument	Is training for the staff planned? Are proposals for such training innovative (i.e., remote training while the service occurs, etc.)?	0-5
c) References and experience of the user group	Research/measurements track-record and professional background	0-5

C. 3 Market-driven access

Criterion	Explanation	Score / Points available
1 - Scientific/Technical value and Innovation		30
a) Scientific and technical quality	Is the proposed work based on a sound knowledge of the state of the art? Is the realization of the proposed solution/work realistic, considering the available knowledge, technical resources and expertise?	0-10
b) Likelihood of developing a new successful technology / product	The extent to which the proposed project will lead to new/improved products, processes or services with clear market potential.	0-10
c) Market potential (Anticipated benefits of the proposed work in comparison to current commercial and emerging technologies)	Is the solution a significant improvement over previous/other ongoing alternatives? Has it some potential to change the dynamic of the market and possibly to address a societal challenge?	0-10
2 - Quality and efficiency of the implementation		15
a) Quality of the workplan and exploitation plan	Appropriateness and rationale of the proposed scientific work. Does the proposed work include a credible path to deliver the (innovative) solution to the market? (i.e. adequacy of plans for commercialization and utilization of the proposed solution). Is there a clear future strategy for	0-5

	knowledge management and protection (IP strategy)?	
b) References, capabilities and experience of the user group/company	Technical/scientific knowledge and experience of the team. Company profile and track-record.	0-5
c) Novel or unconventional access approaches	Degree to which the TNA request proposes novel forms of access (combinations of remote and physical access; simultaneous, hybrid or sequential access to multiple facilities; use of facilities for novel purposes)	0-5

C. 4 Training need-driven access

Criterion	Explanation	Score / Points available
1 - Scientific/learning objectives and motivation		30
a) Relevance of the scientific and training objectives	Appropriateness, motivation, and completeness of the objectives of the proposed training.	0-10
b) Relevance of the training for the user current/future position	Degree to which the training is needed/useful and may have a significant impact on the applicants' career path. Would the applicants utilize knowledge and expertise gained regularly? How are the plans for exploiting the knowledge and skills acquired?	0-10
c) Relevance of the training for the belonging organization (multiplier effect of the training)	Degree to which the training is needed/useful for the operations/developments of the organization the users belong to. Degree to which the applicant could be counted on to further disseminate the knowledge and expertise gained (train the trainer).	0-10
2 - Quality of the applicant		10
a) Academic achievement	Evidence from CV or references of higher degrees, publications, honors, awards and scholarships, research experience. Knowledge and expertise	0-5

b) Research potential	Applicant's ability to conduct independent research and contribute to the field. This can be evaluated based on their research interests, previous research experience, and any publications or conference presentations.	0-5
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B.5 BONUS POINTS added to any application.

BONUS points to be added (by SAMU) to the average scores obtained after review		MAX	Rule for scoring
i) For Gender empowerment	In case of: a) female/non-binary leadership of the user group b) user groups composed of the majority of women c) 50%-50% gender balance in the user group	1	If at least one of a), b), c) is YES then score 1 Otherwise no score
ii) For collaboration and access to new Users	In case of: a) users who have not made previous use of the facilities; b) users working in countries where facilities similar to those requested do not exist. c) users from non-atmospheric/non-academic domains	1	If at least one of a), b), c) is YES then score 1 Otherwise no score.
iii) For involvement of students / young scientists	In case of: a) early career scientists and students at PhD level and below involved in the project	1	If a) is YES, then score 1 Otherwise no score.

